

Introduction to the application of the PARSEC synthesis model: case study from East Africa

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General Context: Earth Observation to Support the SDGs

General Context: Do Protected Areas help or hinder local communities?

PARSEC project: 6 regions across the World

Same goal: before-and-after comparisons to assess causal PA effects

PARSEC project: Goals

Common approach

- Selection of PAs (marine and terrestrial)
- Selection of rural towns and villages
- Long time-series
- Matching algorithm

Different assessments

- Estimate the socioeconomic outcomes
- Track change over time

The PARSEC synthesis methodology

Case study from East Africa ...

- Mozambique
- Tanzania
- Madagascar
- Comoros

Protected Areas selection

- World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA)

Selection criteria :

- Rural - over 50 km from cities of + 20,000 inhabitants
- PAs created/reinforced between 1990 and 2015
- At least 1km²

Many fields poorly documented in WDPA (required manual checking) :

- Status
- Year of creation
- IUCN category
- etc.

Protected Areas selection

16 MPAs selected

orig_name	desig	desig_eng	desig_ty	iucn_cat	int_crit	marine	rep_m_area
Sahamalaza	National Park	National Park	National	Not Reported	Not Applicable	1	0
Salary Bay	Aire marine protégée	Marine Protected Area	National	Not Reported	Not Applicable	2	450,83816
Ifaho	Marine Park	Marine Park	National	II	Not Applicable	1	25
Ambodilaitry Masoala	Marine Park	Marine Park	National	II	Not Applicable	2	21
Barrière de Corail Nosy Ve Androka	Ramsar Site, Wetland of International Importance	Ramsar Site, Wetland of International Importance	International	Not Reported	(i)(ii)(iii)(iv)(vii)(viii)	2	0
Velondriake	Paysage Harmonieux Protégé	Paysage Harmonieux Protégé	National	V	Not Applicable	2	640
Ponta do Ouro	Reserva Nacional	National Reserve	National	Not Reported	Not Applicable	2	704
Quirimbas	Marine Area within buffer zone	Buffer Zone	National	Not Reported	Not Applicable	2	0
Mafia Island	Marine Park	Marine Park	National	VI	Not Applicable	1	615
Tampolo	Marine Park	Marine Park	National	II	Not Applicable	2	32,5643
Ankivonjy	Paysage Harmonieux Protégé	Paysage Harmonieux Protégé	National	V	Not Applicable	2	1368
Ambohibola	Locally Managed Marine Area	Locally Managed Marine Area	National	Not Reported	Not Applicable	2	24,7
Parc National de Mohéli	Parc National	National Park	National	Not Reported	Not Applicable	1	461
Pemba Channel Conservation Area	Area de Conservación	Conservation Area	National	Not Reported	Not Applicable	1	777
Ankarea	Paysage Harmonieux Protégé	Paysage Harmonieux Protégé	National	V	Not Applicable	2	1355
Manjaboaka	Locally Managed Marine Area	Locally Managed Marine Area	National	Not Reported	Not Applicable	1	240

Treated villages selection

Treated villages selection

OpenStreetMap (OSM) database used and enriched to identify villages

Villages were selected if they are:

- within 20 km from the MPA selected
- within 5km from the coast
- over 50/100km from cities +20K inhabitants
- over 100 buildings in size
- over 20km from an MPA not selected

95 villages selected in total (for the 16 MPAs).

Treated villages selection

Number of villages

Madagascar

Mozambique

Comoros

Tanzania

Control (mirror) village selection

- About 3000 possible control villages located:
 - between 20 and 200km from selected MPAs
 - within 15km from the coast
 - over 15km from another MPA

Control (mirror) village selection

Variables used to match treated-control villages

1. Climate : Yearly average of 24 climate variables (1970-2000)
2. Altitude
3. Slope
4. Roughness index
5. Land use from MODIS/ESA (1992-2000)
6. Population in 2000
7. Is the village on an island or on the coast (if on an island: size of the island)
8. Distance to the coast in km
9. Distance to another selected MPA in km
10. Distance to any other protected area in km
(terrestrial or marin), area > 1km², IUCN_category # ('V', 'VI', 'Not Applicable')
11. Distance to a large city (+20K inhab.) in km (based on "worldcities")
12. Travel time to the closest city in 2000 (JRC data)
13. Distance to the closest mangrove (centroid) in km
14. Distance to the closest coral reef (centroid) in km
15. Wealth 1996-00 - to be estimated by Deep Learning model

Yeh et al., (2020)

Article | [Open Access](#) | Published: 22 May 2020

Using publicly available satellite imagery and deep learning to understand economic well-being in Africa

Christopher Yeh, Anthony Perez, Anne Driscoll, George Azzari, Zhongyi Tang, David Lobell, Stefano Ermon & Marshall Burke [✉](#)

Nature Communications **11**, Article number: 2583 (2020) | [Cite this article](#)

13k Accesses | 5 Citations | 121 Altmetric | [Metrics](#)

Reporting summary

Further information on research design is available in the [Nature Research Reporting Summary](#) linked to this article.

Data availability

Data to replicate all findings in the paper are available at https://github.com/sustainlab-group/africa_poverty.

Code availability

Code to replicate all findings in the paper are available at https://github.com/sustainlab-group/africa_poverty.

Using Deep Learning and Earth Observation Data to Estimate Poverty

- Estimate well-being indicators from satellite imagery using Deep Learning

Wealth index construction

DHs surveys

Wealth index construction

Country_Village	Lat	Lon	Household	V ₁	V ₂	...	V _n	WI	WI
C ₁ .Vi ₁			H ₁					Mean	
			H ₂						
			⋮						
			H _n						
C ₁ .Vi ₂			H ₁					Mean	
			H ₂						
			⋮						
			H _n						
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	
C _n .Vi _n			H ₁					Mean	
			H ₂						
			⋮						
			H _n						

Estimated Wealth index

Legend:

C: Country

Vi: Village

V: DHS variable

H: Household

WI: Wealth index

•: Household Location

•: Center village

DHS surveys

- 93 DHS surveys conducted for 25 countries in Africa from 1996 to 2019 (36424 villages)

DHS points

- ☐ **Madagascar:** 1997, 2008, 2011, 2013, 2016
- ☐ **Mozambique:** 2009, 2011, 2015, 2018
- ☐ **Tanzania:** 2003, 2007, 2010, 2012, 2015, 2017
- ☐ **Comoros:** 2012

Satellite images vs Wealth index

Highest wealth

RGB

SWIR1

SWIR2

TEMP1

NIR

DMSP

highest wealth: 2.760691, loc= Angola 2011 (-12.350257, 13.534922)

Lowest wealth

RGB

SWIR1

SWIR2

TEMP1

NIR

VIIRS

lowest wealth: -1.316495, loc = Kenya 2014 (1.179216, 37.148441)

Data preparation

DHS out-of-country

DHS in-country

DHS in-country folds: Distribution by country

Performance analysis of Deep learning estimation

Period	DHS data	R2					
		Resnet-18 MS+NL	Resnet-18 RGB+NL	Resnet-18 NL	Resnet-18 MS	Resnet-18 RGB	KNN NL hist
1996-2019	36424 villages (24 countries)	0,691	0,67	0,66	0,66	0,60	0,64
2009-2016	19669 villages (23 countries)	0,70	-	0,68	0,67	-	0,65
2000-2019	12507 villages- urbain (24 countries)	0,47	-	0,46	0,39	-	-

Wealth index estimation

1. Wealth index annual estimation **for candidates villages** from 1997 to 2001 (3115 villages)

1. Wealth index annual estimation **for selected villages** from 1997 to 2021 (97 pairs)

1. Matching villages

2. Before-and-after comparison

Before-and-after
comparison (work in
progress)

**Spatio-temporal Mapping
of Poverty in Madagascar
using DHS Survey and
Remote Sensing Data
(1996-2020)**

« pixel ≈ 6km »
20527 pixels

Spatio-temporal
Mapping of Poverty in
Madagascar using
DHS Survey and
Remote Sensing Data
(1996-2020)

« District »

Wednesday, October 05th

1:30 p.m

Deep Learning for image analysis

Jeaneth Machicao (Escola Politécnica da USP)
and

Ali Ben Abbes (Foundation for Research on Biodiversity)

Conclusion & futur works

- Using transfer learning strategy of a trained model on Africa's countries to others cases studies (Brazil, Japon, Australia, etc.)
- Using Multi-task learning to estimate others indices with poverty (e.g. education, water, etc.)